
CSCCE Tech Case Study: Using GitHub to maintain a static website (CarpentryCon) or blog (Data Umbrella)

About this case study

In 2023, CSCCE hosted a series of community “Tools Trials” that focused on tools commonly used for community management in open-source and open-source-supporting communities. The goal of the series - which consisted of several live webinars with Q&A and this accompanying tip sheet collection - was to share existing knowledge and provide any scientific community manager with options about tools and use cases they could explore further.

One of the most commonly used tools by these communities is GitHub. In this case study, we summarize how two organizations, The Carpentries and Data Umbrella, make use of GitHub as a platform to host website materials on which their members can collaborate.

What is GitHub?

[GitHub](#) is a version control platform for storing, collaborating on, and tracking projects. It is primarily used for software development, but can also be used for other collaborative work. It utilizes [Git](#), which is an open-source version control system that can track which users make changes to computer files (e.g., code, documents) and when. Although there are other software platforms that use Git, GitHub is the most popular. [Check out our introductory tip sheet for more information.](#)

Overview of CarpentryCon

CarpentryCon is a semi-regular gathering of members of [The Carpentries](#) community who are interested in upskilling to support a range of community activities. The event has taken place both in-person and online and invites community members to participate in the creation of the conference agenda (described in a separate [case study in this series](#)), which includes standard sessions, workshops, and discussions.

Overview of Data Umbrella

[Data Umbrella](#) serves data scientists from under-represented communities, and offers educational resources and networking for its members. They run regular webinars on a range of topics, host a Meetup group for members to connect at local events, and convene online conversations on GitHub and Discord.

Getting Started

To get started, a user can copy (or “fork” using GitHub terminology) a blog of interest, or they can find themes which are publicly available ([Jekyll themes](#), [Hugo](#), [Jamstack](#) are some options). Then, the code can be customized for a particular use case.

The CarpentryCon website

All of The Carpentries’ websites are built using a tool (i.e., static site generator, SSG) which converts raw data files plus website templates into web pages. This allows an entire website, including the code (JavaScript, CSS, HTML) and the site content (text and images) to be stored on GitHub. This provides a convenient way of reusing and customizing existing templates at the same time as making it possible for members to suggest updates to the site by opening an issue or submitting a pull request (you can find a glossary of GitHub terms in our overview tip sheet). The CarpentryCon 2022 site was built using an existing [template](#) and is hosted by [Jekyll](#), an open-source static site generator.

Figure 1

A screenshot of the [repository](#) used to house the files that built the [CarpentryCon 2022 website](#).

The Data Umbrella blog

Data Umbrella also uses a combination of GitHub and Jekyll for their website, and they use GitHub to support the [collaborative creation of blog posts](#). The blog is used to communicate updates to the community, write reports on workshops, and provide summaries for funders. It is also used to document any key learnings, share community interviews, and cross-post any blogs written by community members on Data Umbrella events. Contributors to the blog include Data Umbrella team members and community members.

Data Umbrella PyMC 2022-2023 Study Group Report

Summary of the PyMC Open Source Study Groups

3 Lessons from 3 Years of Data Science

Learn of 3 lessons to build your career in data science

Bayesian Data Analysis with BRMS (Bayesian Regression Models Using Stan)

Quickly build robust models for data analysis and prediction using BRMS

Reproducible Publications with Python and Quarto

A tutorial by Thomas Mock of Posit.

Let's Talk Community with Yanina Belline Saibene

Discussion with Yanina on what makes a community

Let's Talk Community with Mariatta Wijaya

Discussion with Mariatta on what makes a community

Figure 2

A screenshot of Data Umbrella's blog, which is built using a combination of Jekyll and GitHub.

There are two common ways that Data Umbrella community members collaborate on blog posts:

1. Contributors begin a blog in a shared document (e.g., a Google document). When it has been drafted, they submit a pull request in GitHub to inform community contributors, who can then submit comments directly in the Google doc.
2. A contributor begins writing a blog post in GitHub using an issue template or by modeling after another blog post on the Data Umbrella site, adding the content and sharing with the team for review and comment.

In all cases, the final version is reviewed and approved by the community manager, who adds any edits (using Markdown) needed to format the post and then merges the pull request in GitHub, which publishes the final version of the blog post to the Data Umbrella website.

Pros and cons of using GitHub for this use case

[For general pros and cons of using GitHub for community management, [please refer to our overview tip sheet.](#)]

Pros:

- All website code and content is stored in a public repo, so community members can contribute to the upkeep of the site or blog.
- There are lots of existing templates that you can use to generate your website.

Cons:

- Using GitHub to create a website or blog requires working knowledge of the coding languages Markdown, HTML, and CSS, as well as a more in-depth understanding of GitHub.

Additional resources

- [Maneesha Sane's full presentation on GitHub for CarpentryCon](#) – Watch this case study being presented during CSCCE's Tools Trial in this short video
- [Reshama Shaikh's full presentation on using GitHub to create the Data Umbrella blog](#) – Watch this case study being presented during CSCCE's Tools Trial in this short video
- Static site generators:
 - [Jekyll](#)
 - [Quarto](#)
- Deployment options:
 - GitHub Pages
 - [Netlify](#)
- Jekyll themes: <https://jekyllthemes.io/>
- Data Umbrella blog code: <https://github.com/data-umbrella/data-umbrella.github.io>
- Video tutorial on creating a free blog using Jekyll and GitHub: <https://youtu.be/7SBXI94xNI8>
- Using Markdown: https://github.com/reshamas/ds_resources/blob/master/markdown/examples_of_markdown.md

Note

This tip sheet focuses on specific technologies to share experiences, examples, and a place for users to get started. However, there are other options for hosting code (such as GitLab), deployment options, and static site generators (SSG).

Acknowledgements

This case study is based on presentations by Reshama Shaikh (Data Umbrella) and Maneesha Sane (The Carpentries). CSCCE uses the CRediT contributor roles taxonomy to show how the authors listed contributed to the creation of this guide:

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Citing and reusing this tip sheet

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Cite as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2024) Tech Case Study: Using GitHub to maintain a static website (CarpentryCon) or blog (Data Umbrella). Shaikh, Pratt, Sane, Lescak, Crall, and Woodley doi: [10.5281/zenodo.12117886](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12117886)

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Last updated June 2024